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18 **CE Database subject headings:** Fishways; Water level; Hydraulic design; Simulation
19 models; Hydraulic structures.

20 **Introduction**

21 Loss of longitudinal connectivity by man-made obstructions is one of the main ecological
22 problems in regulated rivers (Nilsson et al. 2005; Branco et al. 2012). This issue particularly
23 affects migratory fish, which require different environments for the principal stages of their
24 life cycle (Porcher and Travade 2002). However, the social benefits of these obstacles make it
25 impractical to remove them and often, the only way to restore longitudinal connectivity, at
26 least partly, is by building fish passes (Wang et al. 2010; Calluad et al. 2012).

27 One of the most widely used fish passes are vertical slot fishways (VSFs). These structures
28 are widespread mainly due to their capacity to cope with different flows (Tarrade et al. 2011)
29 and their versatility regarding the water depth available for upstream fish movement (Liu et
30 al. 2006). VSF consists on an open channel divided into a number of pools by cross-walls
31 equipped with vertical slots. This configuration divides the total height of the obstacle into
32 small head drops (ΔH) and forms a jet at slots, the energy of which is dissipated by mixing in
33 pools (Liu et al. 2006).

34 Based on their geometric configuration, there are many types of VSFs (Rajaratnam et al.
35 1986; Rajaratnam et al. 1992; Wu et al. 1999; Puertas et al. 2004). However, the most
36 common configuration is that of the Hell's Gate model, with double or single slots (model 1
37 according to Rajaratnam et al. (1986)) (Fig. 1).

38 a) 39 **Fig. 1.** Schematic representation of Hell's Gate model with a single slot (model 1 defined by
 40 Rajaratnam et al. 1996), the model under study. a) Plant. b) Longitudinal section. c) Cross section.
 41 Note: The symbols are defined in the notation section.

42 In some cases, the flow of VSFs is described by the equation for weirs proposed by Poleni
 43 (1717) (FAO/DVWK 2002; Krüger et al. 2010), discounting in the discharge coefficient (C_1)
 44 the effect of the lower contraction (Eq. (1)). In other cases, their flow can also be compared to
 45 that of a submerged orifice with an area equal to the product of the width (b) and the water
 46 level upstream the slot (h_1) (Eq. (2)) (Martínez de Azagra 1999; Larinier 2002; Bermúdez et
 47 al. 2010; Wang et al. 2010) and discounting in the discharge coefficient (C_2) the effect of
 48 contractions.

49
$$Q = \frac{2}{3} \cdot C_1 \cdot b \cdot h_1^{1.5} \cdot \sqrt{2 \cdot g} \quad (1)$$

50
$$Q = C_2 \cdot b \cdot h_1 \cdot \sqrt{2 \cdot g \cdot \Delta H} \quad (2)$$

51 In both equations the discharge coefficients (C_1 and C_2) depend on the relative position of the
 52 water levels (upstream and downstream (h_2)) and the geometry of the VSF, while g stands for
 53 the acceleration due to gravity.

54 In 1986 and 1992 Rajaratnam et al., by using the geometry of the slots, proposed the use of
 55 dimensionless relationships to describe discharge in VSFs (Eq. (3) and Eq. (4)).

56
$$Q^* = \frac{Q}{\sqrt{g \cdot S \cdot b^5}} \quad (3)$$

57
$$Q^* = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot (h_0/b) \quad (4)$$

58 where β_0 and β_1 depend on the geometry of the VSF, h_0 is the mean water depth (measured at
59 the center of the pool), S is the slope and Q^* is the dimensionless discharge. These
60 relationships have widely been used (Puertas et al. 2004; Cea et al. 2007) and modified (Wu
61 et al. 1999; Kamula 2001).

62 Given the variability in the factors that describe their flow, VSFs behave differently both
63 amongst them and throughout time. Consequently, it is a common practice to simplify their
64 study by using geometrically perfect laboratory models with uniform flow conditions, where
65 ΔH is the same in all the slots and equal to topographic difference between slots (Δz)
66 (Rajaratnam et al. 1986; Rajaratnam et al. 1992; Wu et al. 1999; Puertas et al. 2004; Cea et al.
67 2007; Bermúdez et al. 2010; Tarrade et al. 2011; Puertas et al. 2012).

68 These operational characteristics are difficult to achieve under laboratory conditions and, even
69 more, in real-world conditions. In many cases, due to an inaccurate execution or simply
70 because the ideal working situation is never encountered, fish passes will work under non-
71 uniform flow conditions which may decrease their efficiency for fish passage.

72 In order to overcome these limitations, the present study aims to improve the modeling of
73 VSFs' hydraulic performance using the equation proposed by Villemonte (1947), to evaluate
74 the influence of downstream water level, together with a logical algorithm. This will allow to
75 estimate the distribution of water depths in both geometrically and not geometrically perfect
76 VSFs (i.e. different Δz between slots, different b in each slot, etc.), under different uniform or
77 non-uniform flow states.

78 **Materials and Methods**

79 *Experimental Arrangement and Experiments*

80 Experiments were conducted in two VSFs of Hell's Gate type designed by the Group of

81 Applied Ecohydraulics of the University of Valladolid. Both VSFs are located on two weirs in
82 the Duero River (North-Central Spain). In the first one (VSF1 – 41°37'N, 4°6'W) a succession
83 of 27 slots were studied (n=27), while in the second one (VSF2 – 41°38'N, 3°34'W) a
84 succession of 12 (n=12).

85 The geometrical parameters of the VSFs were measured by topographic surveying (Fig. 1).
86 Both VSFs are composed by pools of a mean length of 2.100 m ($L \approx 10 \cdot b$) and a mean width
87 of 1.600 m ($B = 8 \cdot b$). The average width of slots is 0.200 m and the mean Δz is 0.143 m for
88 VSF1 and 0.189 m for VSF2 with an average slope ($S = \Delta z / (L + e)$, where e is the thickness of
89 the cross-wall) of 0.062 m/m and 0.082 m/m, respectively.

90 During the experimental procedures the flow rate was controlled by the gates located
91 upstream the structures and was measured by chemical gaging using Rhodamine WT as tracer
92 (Martínez 2001). These gates are used for the maintenance and cleaning in both fishways,
93 however they provide the opportunity to represent in the same season different hydrodynamic
94 scenarios, that is to say different h_1 in the first slot ($h_{1,1}$) and discharges through the fishways.

95 This type of experiment was replicated four times to achieve in each VSF different non-
96 uniform water depth distribution profiles (conceptual backwater profile (M1) and drawdown
97 profile (M2) (Rajaratnam et al. 1986; Chow 2004)) (Table 1). M1 profiles were obtained by
98 reducing the area of the slot situated downstream the last slot studied (increasing h_2 of the last
99 slot studied ($h_{2,n}$)) and M2 and uniform (U) profiles were naturally present during the
100 experiments.

101 **Table 1.** Results of discharge experiments in VSF-1 and VSF-2. $h_{2,n}$ is the downstream water depth in
 102 the last slot studied (when modeling the performance equal to tailwater level).

Experiment name	Estimated discharge \pm CI (m^3/s)	Reached Profile	$h_{2,n}$ (m)
VSF1-1	0.247 ± 0.004	M2	0.700
VSF1-2	0.247 ± 0.004	M1	0.979
VSF1-3	0.247 ± 0.004	M1	1.029
VSF1-4	0.165 ± 0.010	M1	0.617
VSF2-1	0.232 ± 0.004	U	0.729
VSF2-2	0.232 ± 0.004	M1	0.858
VSF2-3	0.276 ± 0.007	U	0.816
VSF2-4	0.276 ± 0.007	M1	0.990

103

104 The water depth was measured in each pool by a graduate scale situated downstream the slots
 105 in the center of the cross-walls. In each pool successive measures were made to obtain a stable
 106 mean value.

107 *Discharge Coefficient*

108 Villemonte (1947) described the net flow over a submerged weir as the difference between
 109 the free-flow discharge due to h_1 and the free-flow discharge due to h_2 . Taking into account
 110 the assumptions of this author and that under free-flow discharge Eq. (2) becomes Eq. (1) (ΔH
 111 tends to h_1), the discharge coefficient for both equations can be defined as,

$$112 \quad C = \alpha_0 \cdot \left(1 - \left(\frac{h_2}{h_1} \right)^{1.5} \right)^{\alpha_1} \quad (5)$$

113 where α_0 and α_1 are coefficients which depend on the geometry of the slot and the discharge
 114 equation used.

115 Although this coefficient was initially described by Villemonte for weirs, Krüger et al. (2010)
 116 showed the suitability of similar expressions in the description of the functioning of VSFs.

117 **Formulation of the algorithm**

118 To simulate the water depth distributions of the VSFs under different hydrodynamic
 119 scenarios, taking into account the specific geometrical characteristics of each slot, it is
 120 necessary to perform an iterative bottom-up calculus considering the discharge through the
 121 fishway (Q_{fishway}) (or the headwater level ($h_{1,1}$)) and $h_{2,n}$ (Fig. 2).

122 Fig. 2 represents the logical algorithm followed in order to solve a particular scenario where
 123 Eq. (6) represents each of the discharge equations proposed. Due to the iterative process, the
 124 resolution of the algorithm can be tedious; thus, its programming is highly recommended.
 125 Consequently, a computer program called “Escalas 2012” was developed (Fuentes-Pérez et al.
 126 2012).

127
 128 **Fig. 2.** Flowchart showing the steps of the proposed algorithm. Note: The symbols are defined
 129 in the notation section.

130 **Validation**

131 The fit of the proposed discharge equations was evaluated using r-squared (r^2) with data
 132 collected both from the specialized literature and field measurements (Fig. 3). The
 133 comparison of the predicted water depth profiles using the algorithm and each of the adjusted
 134 equations was carried out by comparing the mean relative errors (MRE) for each scenario.

135 **Experimental Results and Discussion**

136 **Discharge Equations**

137 Fig. 3 shows the fitted curves for the proposed equations. All of them represent part of the
 138 observed variability due to S for the different VSF models (Wang et al. 2010); either because
 139 they describe the variability of ΔH (or h_2), which in uniform settings is determined by S (Fig.
 140 3 (a and b)) or because S is included in the equation (Fig. 3(c) and Eq. (3)). This enables the
 141 use of the equations in fishways with different slope.

142
 143 **Fig. 3.** Discharge equations adjustment. a) Fit of C_1 for the Hell's Gate, 3 and 16 models defined by
 144 Rajaratnam et al. (1996). b) Fit of C_2 for Hell's Gate model. c) Fit of Eq. 4 for Hell's Gate model.

145 As h_2/h_1 approaches zero (h_2 tends to 0), h_1 will reach the critical water depth while C_1 and C_2
 146 will tend to a constant value. C_1 explains well the variability due to h_2 . Regarding C_2 , despite
 147 the small r^2 , it provides satisfactory results when the water depth and head drop profiles of the
 148 fishway are simulated (Fig. 4). This is because Eq. (2) considers, partly, the effect of the
 149 water level distribution (by means of ΔH) providing, even when using a constant value for C_2 ,
 150 more satisfactory results, under non-uniform situations, than the other discharge equations.

151

152 **Fig. 4.** Observed and predicted ΔH and h_1 profiles using the algorithm for VSF1-1 according to the
 153 different equations. Horizontal distance represents the separation between slots and in 0 is situated the
 154 upper slot.

155 In contrast to Eq. (1) and Eq. (2), Eq. (3) does not directly consider water depth in the slot.
 156 The variability of water depth is explained by Eq. (4) by means of h_0 , and thus provides a
 157 higher r^2 than the other adjustments (Fig. 3(c)). Furthermore, Eq. (4) dismisses all the
 158 variability provided by h_2 , making it only possible to explain strictly uniform flow conditions
 159 (Rajaratnam et al. 1986). In order to interpret non-uniform scenarios, it is interesting to adapt
 160 data from the literature to include variables such as h_2 as shown in Fig. 3(a) (model 3 and 16).

161 ***Water depth and head drop profiles***

162 Fig. 4 underlines the importance of considering parameters that take into account the
 163 hydrodynamic conditions of the slot, that is, either h_1 and h_2 or h_1 and ΔH . Weir and orifice
 164 equations (Eq. (1) and Eq. (2)) together with Villemonte's discharge coefficient (Eq. (5)) are
 165 able to describe well the observed ΔH profiles (Fig. 4(a)) and are capable of capturing
 166 changes in $h_{2,n}$ (MRE for all experiments of 8.88% and 8.93%, respectively). However the
 167 dimensionless equations (Eq. (3) and Eq. (4)) do not simulate properly the observed values as
 168 shown by the high MRE for ΔH (40.25%).

169 Regarding h_1 (Fig. 4(b)), weir and orifice equations predict a similar profile to the one
 170 observed (MRE of 1.87% and 2.17%, respectively). With the dimensionless equations, the

171 MRE is higher (5.84 %) and it increases as the influence of $h_{2,n}$ rises. Moreover, when using
172 dimensionless equations the described profile is considerably different to the observed one.

173 **Conclusions**

174 The proposed discharge coefficients enable, using a logical algorithm, the modeling of the
175 performance of both geometrically and not geometrically perfect VSFs under uniform and
176 non-uniform scenarios. Furthermore, this methodology has been evaluated successfully by the
177 experimental study of two existing structures as well as analyzing cases from the literature.

178 According to the results presented here, Eq. (1) and Eq. (2) together with the discharge
179 coefficients defined by Villemonte (1947) (specific to each type of VSF) provide the best
180 option to design and evaluate VSFs.

181 To get accurate water depth predictions it is essential to use equations which include a
182 variable that considers downstream water level (h_2 or ΔH). This provides a means to
183 incorporate both the variation in water levels as well as, given the relationship between S and
184 ΔH in uniform stages, the different slopes used in the design.

185 The use of these discharge coefficients allows the simulation of the distributions of both water
186 levels and head drops in VSFs. This will enable to evaluate the behavior of different solutions
187 prior or after their construction and detect and correct deficiencies in fishway designs.

188 Finally, in order to evaluate the performance and wider applicability of the proposed
189 formulations it would be interesting to apply it to other fishways with different hydraulic
190 connections between pools.

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195 **Notation**

196 The following symbols are used in this technical note:

197 B = width of pools (m)

198 b = slot width (m)

199 b_i = slot i width (m)

200 C = generic discharge coefficient

201 C_1 = discharge coefficient for Eq. (1)

202 C_2 = discharge coefficient for Eq. (2)

203 e = thickness of the cross-wall (m)

204 g = acceleration due to gravity (m/s^2)

205 h_0 = mean water depth of flow in pool in relation to the center of the pool (m)

206 h_1 = mean water depth of flow in pool in relation to the upstream of the slot (m)

207 $h_{1,i}$ = mean water depth of flow in pool in relation to the upstream of the slot i (m)

208 h_2 = mean water depth of flow in pool in relation to the downstream of the slot (m)

209 $h_{2,i}$ = mean water depth of flow in pool in relation to the downstream of the slot i (m)

210 i = slot number

211 CI = 95% confidence interval

212 L = pool length (m)

213 $L_{i-1,i}$ = pool length between slot i and slot $i-1$ (m)

214 n = total number of slots

215 Q = discharge or flow rate (m^3/s)

216 Q^* = dimensionless discharge

217 Q_{fishway} = discharge through fishway (m^3/s)

218 Q_i = discharge through slot i (m^3/s)

219	r^2	=	determination coefficient
220	S	=	slope of the fishway (m/m)
221	α_0	=	dimensionless coefficient for Eq. (5)
222	α_1	=	dimensionless exponent for Eq. (5)
223	β_0, β_1	=	dimensionless coefficients for Eq. (4)
224	ΔH	=	difference in water level between pools or head drop ($h_1 - h_2$) (m)
225	ΔH_i	=	difference in water level between pools or head drop in the slot i ($h_{1,i} - h_{2,i}$) (m)
226	Δz	=	topographic difference between slots (m)
227	$\Delta z_{i-1,i}$	=	topographic difference between slots $i-1$ and i (m)

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